

Influence of 5-Dimensional service quality on customer Delightedness at Yamaha Motors

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ABSTRACT

Service quality has been considered as one of the highest metric for the organizational success. Every organization strives to achieve excellence through the means of satisfying the customers.

OBJECTIVES: The present study try to see the impact of service quality on customer delightedness. The five Service quality Dimensions are Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy.

METHODS/STATISTICAL TOOL :The researcher uses personal and direct method to collect the data.

FINDINGS: The result shows that Customer satisfaction is one of the key issues being monitored by every service provider. Through customer satisfaction and loyalty surveys the managing level of a business can ensure a way of knowing what the customer thinks about their service and what needs to be changed to gain positive customer satisfaction.

Introduction

Yamaha Motor made its initial foray into India in 1985 as a joint-venture. In August 2001, it became a 100% subsidiary of Yamaha Motor Co., Ltd, Japan (YMC). In 2008, Mitsui & Co. Ltd. entered into an agreement with YMC to become a joint-investor in India Yamaha Motor Private Limited (IYM).

IYM's manufacturing facilities comprise of 3 State-of-the-art Plants at Surajpur (Uttar Pradesh), Faridabad (Haryana) and Kanchipuram (Tamil Nadu). The infrastructure at these plants supports production of two-wheelers and parts for the domestic as well as overseas markets.

The **automotive industry in India** is one of the largest in the world with an annual production of 23.96 million vehicles in FY (fiscal year) 2015–16, following a growth of 2.57

per cent over the last year. The automobile industry accounts for 7.1 per cent of the country's gross domestic product (GDP). The Two Wheelers segment, with 81 per cent market share, is the leader of the Indian Automobile market, owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector. The overall Passenger Vehicle (PV) segment has 13 per cent market share.

Need for the Study:

Service quality has been considered as one of the highest metric for the organizational success. All most every organization strives to achieve excellence through the means of satisfying the customers – what we are calling as customer delightedness. In this context the present project plays important role in understanding the impressions of service quality on the customer delightedness.

Customer are the key figure in the business world. The customer came into existence when communications were difficult with the employees and it is found necessary to have a point of distribution. It helps to find out the position of the company in the competitive market and the opinion of the employees towards the **Yamaha Automobiles**.

Customer Satisfaction plays the present competitive Markets .In the present situation, the customer satisfaction will influence employee preferences .I think that there is need to study regarding the customer satisfaction towards **Yamaha Automobiles** because these are the main aspects which should be considered by the company to build its brand name in the market and concentrate on the aspects which can make the customer to be aware of their brand , to know the factors influencing their preferences.

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the existing service quality effectiveness in Yamaha Store.
- To study the impact of service quality on customer delightedness.
- To suggest recommendations to ensure effective service quality to gain competitive advantage.

Scope of the Study:

- The scope of the study is restricted to one Chevrolet Showroom located in Kadapa City. The project fellow met all the required number of customers by visiting frequently the showroom at working hours. The major reasons for restricting the study to one showroom is time and budgetary constraints.

Research Methodology

Primary Data :the data has been collected through questionnaire. Personal interview has been used for data collection .The Secondary Data used in the study is collected through Internet, Books, Published Articles , Journals, Newspaper Articles

SAMPLE SIZE: The sample size of the project is 20 Customers.

Random sampling method of sampling was adopted to get over limitations. The researcher followed the sampling technique, sample random sampling method for the study.

CONTACT METHOD: Personal / direct

Statistical tool: percentage analysis has used to analyse the data. This is simple in nature and provides clear picture about a huge population by breaking it in percentage (Per 100)

Number of Respondents

$$\text{Percentage method} = \frac{\text{Number of Respondents} \times 100}{\text{Total Respondents}}$$

Data analysis and Interpretation

1)TANGIBLES

- Should have up-to-date equipment (yes / no)
- physically facilities should be visually appealing (yes / no)
- Employees should be well dressed and appear neat (yes / no)
- Appearance of physical facilities should be in keeping with the type of service provided (yes / no)

2) RELIABILITY QUALITY

- when customers have problems they should be sympathetic and reassuring (yes / no)
- should be dependable (yes / no)
- should provide their services at the time they promise (yes / no)
- should keep accurate records (yes / no)

3) RESPONSIVENESS QUALITY

- should not be expected to tell customers exactly when services will be performed (yes / no)
- Not realistic for customers to expect prompt service (yes / no)
- Employees do not always have to be willing to help customers (yes / no)
- Is ok if they are too busy to respond to requests promptly (yes / no)

4) ASSURANCE QUALITY

- Customers should be able to trust employees (yes / no)
- Customers should feel safe in their transactions with these stores (yes / no)
- The employees should be polite (yes / no)
- Employees should get adequate support to do their jobs well (yes / no)

5) EMPATHY QUALITY

- Company should not be expected to give customers individual attention (yes / no)
- Employees cannot be expected to give customers personal attention (yes / no)
- Unrealistic to expect employees to know what the needs of their customers (yes / no)

- Should not be expected to have operating hours convenient to all customers (yes / no)

Conclusion

1)Tangibles Quality: This quotient speaks about ‘appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials’. In this organization, with regard to this quotient the results are like this:

- organization is using updated equipment for serving the customers.
- Physical facilities are also visually appealing
- The ambience of the organization is also attractive.

2)Reliability Quality: This quotient speaks about ‘ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately’. The results relating to this quotient are:

- No issues relating to delayed assignments.
- The organizational employees have sympathetic sense towards understanding the customer urgencies.
- Visible timely service.
- They are also kept the accurate records.

3)Responsiveness Quality: This facet deals with ‘willingness to help customers and provide prompt service’. The results regarding to this quotient are:

- Customers are quiet happy with service performance.
- Every time the organization is doing prompt service.
- Employees are always cooperative and friendly with the customers.
- Service requests are promptly addressed.

4) Assurance Quality: This factor concerns about ‘knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. The responses on this quotient are:

- Customers expressed visible trust on employees
- Customers are happy with the transactions security and employees are also particular about it.
- Employees behave so politely with the customers.
- Employees get adequate support from all dimensions to perform their job well.

5) Empathy Quality: This quotient deals with ‘caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers’. The results relating to this quotient are:

- Company always pays ‘individual attention’ on their customers.
- Employees are specific about paying ‘personal attention’ on customers.
- Customers understand the unrealistic expectations about service deliverables.
- The firm is maintaining convenient operating hours to provide service to their customers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following imperatives are suggested based on the discussion of results :-

- Even though organization is taking enough care about providing quality services; special concentration is required in framing service schedules.
- “Loyal Customers” should be given non-monetary appreciation.
- Sessions like Customer-Employee interactions must be frequently arranged.
- Service on Call or Mail should be introduced.
- New innovations in the service quality enhancement ought to be encouraged.
- Customer feedback forms must be evaluated by using 360 degree method i.e. so that all the employees will get awareness on changing customer perceptions and requirements in service accomplishments.

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